

Research Perspective: Contribution from the ACUTE Knowledge Hub

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While the academic literature on the 15-minute City is growing, and the concept is gaining momentum in current urban practice, the link between ongoing research and the practices of urban professionals is neither direct, immediate nor straightforward. This contribution aims to fill this gap by reporting on the key findings of a series of seminars organised by the authors, which served as dynamic forums, bringing together urban practitioners and academics. The seminars were organised as part of the wider ACUTE (Accessibility and Connectivity for Urban Transformation of Europe) project, which aims to promote the exchange of experience between practitioners from institutions, the private sector, NGOs, citizens and the research community on urban and mobility issues.

The ACUTE project is a multi-stakeholder project composed of partners of five European countries, coordinated by BOKU – University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Institute of Production and Logistics, Vienna (AT). Its partners comprise Université Gustave Eiffel (FR), Cerema (FR), Latvia University of Life Sciences and Technologies, University of Latvia, RISE – Research Institutes of Sweden, University of Westminster (UK), Malmö University (SWE), K2 (SWE), Power Circle (SWE), University of Innsbruck (AT) and Graz Energy Agency (AT).

ACUTE aims at:

- Informing non-academics about a wide range of the latest research about Accessible and Connected City
- Providing documentation and scientific support to practitioners in their daily practice
- Collecting 15-minute City's experiences, to group in a single location and contribute to overcoming the fragmentation of knowledge on the 15-minute City topic

The 15-minute City raises many research questions and appears to be a solution for making cities more accessible.

The development of the knowledge hub involved a comprehensive approach, encompassing an extensive review of the literature and an exploration of current research projects. The knowledge hub is actively shaping its identity through seminars, facilitating a direct exchange of insights, experiences, and perspectives; we seek to forge a more seamless connection between the evolving body of research on the 15-minute City and its practical integration into urban planning and development. Since the project began at the end of 2022, two seminars – one in Milan (03/2023) and one in Antwerp (10/2023) – open to scientists and practitioners, and a workshop, have been organised. The seminars attracted 115 academics and 33 practitioners from 14 countries.

First Results

The ACUTE project identified five research topics:

- 1) Defining the 15-minute city
- 2) Selecting the transport modes of the 15-minute city
- 3) Integrating proximity into urban planning
- 4) Supporting inclusiveness in the 15-minute city
- 5) Evaluating the 15-minute city

1. The definition of the 15-minute City

In the scientific literature, the 15-minute City tends to be defined as accessibility through proximity, as opposed to increasing accessibility through mobility. A consensual basis for the definition considers the access to essential services in less than or equal to 15 minutes on foot or by bicycle, but the recent research developments add an emphasis on the issues of decarbonation and inclusiveness. Faced with the challenges of adapting cities to climate change and combating urban sprawl, the concept of the city of proximity is receiving renewed attention in urban planning. This is due to its relevance to the challenges of reducing CO₂ emissions in mobility practices, as well as in terms of inclusiveness, both for people with reduced mobility and for groups identified as vulnerable. The latter are confronted with an urban design, and a spatial and temporal distribution of amenities that are often not adapted to their needs, and this has repercussions on their mobility behaviour.

2. What modes of transport for the city of proximity?

An urban design that encourages cycling, walking and access to public transport services is at the core of the city of proximity, which also includes universality and inclusiveness. Proximity entails also an idea of flexibility that feeds on the idea that essential services vary according to the urban context. To implement the 15-minute City model, it is essential to integrate proximity in the broad sense of the term (i.e. geographical, spatial, social, perceptual and temporal) into urban development.

3. Integrating proximity into urban planning

To integrate proximity into urban planning, public authorities must intervene to create accessible, safe and well-served neighbourhoods for pedestrians and cyclists, as well as high quality public spaces and services that encourage local life. This can be quantified by assessing accessibility and urban conditions, both within cities and in outlying areas. There needs to be constant dialogue between public authority decision-makers and the needs of users, particularly groups identified as vulnerable because of their gender, physical and/or mental conditions and socio-economic conditions.

4. Supporting inclusiveness in the 15-minute city

Participating in urban life implies being able to access activities and public space. In this regard, many inequalities exist: women, for instance, often refer to the feeling of security as a barrier to movement, to access and finally to taking part to urban activities. Identifying the needs of vulnerable groups is essential to making the city of proximity inclusive. In addition, the integration of the gender dimension plays an important role, particularly as there is a lack of knowledge about the link between gender and walking. With this in mind, a gender-specific walkability indicator has been developed in Milan around the collaborative application "Wher", as part of the European project [STEP UP](#). This application aims to map the perceptions of safety in public spaces of people who identify themselves as women.

Another example of a tool for measuring inclusiveness is the IAPI (Inclusive Accessibility by Proximity Index) indicator developed as part of the European EXTRA project, which combines walkability, access to services in 5, 10 and 15 minutes, and the perception and quality of the urban environment, according to transport mode and conditions, walking, reduced mobility and cycling. The city of proximity is also a city where children can move around safely, using the modes mentioned. However, it is observed that children's use of public spaces is strongly influenced by their parents' perception of their safety.

5. Evaluating the City of Proximity

Two explicit approaches to evaluating the city of proximity using indicators were presented at the ACUTE seminars:

1. The "Women's Walkability Index" (WWI), currently being developed as part of the STEP UP project, will combine perception and GIS measurements to access facilities as part of a 15-minute City approach
2. The IAPI (Inclusive Accessibility by Proximity Index) developed as part of the Extra project and mentioned above from the point of view of inclusiveness, aims to assess the impact of experiences of travelling on foot, by bicycle or with reduced mobility in the streets of Bologna.

Remaining challenges

During one workshop, a discussion on the issue of the diversity of urban contexts evolved. The 15-minute City is generally recognised as a suitable urban model for dense urban areas, but also suitable for smaller size urban cores where the full range of basic services can be found in a compact setting. The challenge of improving the connectivity and accessibility of peripheral areas brings the notion of adaptability and flexibility to urban contexts to the heart of the 15-minute City concept. Solutions are envisaged for peripheral areas:

- ▶ Setting up multimodal hubs integrating shared mobility systems, micro-mobility and public transport services
- ▶ Development of pedestrian and cycling infrastructures
- ▶ Improving the reliability of mobility information using digital solutions

At the workshop, practitioners expressed a very strong concern about the various expressions of social resistance and backlash against the 15-minute city in European cities. This is a clear expression of the need for knowledge about these phenomena.

Several contributions proposed digital tools to facilitate the daily management of mobility, with a focus on prioritising active transport modes. However, these solutions may be limited in that they are less inclusive in their use.

The notion of proximity is central to the definition of the 15-minute City. Proximity planning is much more feasible in dense, multifunctional urban spaces than in peripheral, low-density areas. The most striking aspect found during our investigation is the idea that the research on the 15-minute City concepts tend to put the focus on particular, contextual needs, as opposed to a standardised, uniformed, functional approach. The concept also raises the question: The 15-minute City, for whom? Developing transport infrastructure and linking it to urban development designed by and for users seems relevant to achieve the goal of improving accessibility and inclusivity of cities.

The concept of the 15-minute City raises many research questions and appears to be a solution for making cities more accessible. In this perspective, it is important to think about ways to avoid the fragmentation of knowledge in order to promote links between research and practice in urban planning and mobility. The permeability between research and practice is necessary for the implementation of resilient actions to make cities more accessible and inclusive. The ACUTE project aims to create a knowledge hub to strengthen the link between research results and urban development issues.

Further Readings

Büttner, B. & Seisenberger, S. (2023): The Inclusive ± 15-Minute City. [Link](#)

Choubassi, R., Gorrini, A., Gargiulo, C., Guida, C., Andreola, F.N., Muzzonigro, A., Gargiulo, E., Walker, J. (2023). Walkability for Women and the 15- minute City Framework: The STEP UP Project. [Link](#)

Lanza, G., Pucci, P., Carboni, L. (2023): From mobility to accessibility by proximity: an Inclusive Accessibility by Proximity Index (I-API)*. [Link](#)

L'Hostis, A., Cissé, N.A., Hachette, M. (2023). The 15-Minute City: A New Avatar of Proximity and a Pillar of the European Urban Transition. [Link](#)

Rauli, A., Büttner, B. Silva, S, Seisenberger, S. (2023): Defining Proximity-centred Accessibility. [Link](#)

Wassim, H. & L'Hostis, A. (2022). Mobility Hubs, a Lever for More Sustainable Mobility? [Link](#)